

D2.3

Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value chains

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 Research question.....	8
1.2 Preliminary considerations.....	8
1.3 Aim	8
1.4 Structure of the document	9
2. APPROACH	10
2.1 Methodology.....	10
2.2 Additional considerations.....	10
3. LITERATURE REVIEW	13
3.1 Sustainability and the role of certification	13
3.2 Specialised literature on biofuels and other bio-based commodities 16	
3.3 Gravity models	17
4. CONCLUSIONS	23
4.1 Concluding remarks	23
4.2 Recommendations.....	23
REFERENCES	24
ANNEX	28

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Channels of potential VSS impact on trade.	13
Figure 2: VSS and SDG targets..	14

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Relevant search terms.....	10
Table 2: Key characteristics of selected contributions	11
Table 3: Coverage and data sources	12
Table 4: Specifying a gravity model – selected examples.....	19
Table 5: Literature review	28

ABBREVIATIONS

APEC	Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation
CARICOM	Caribbean Community
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ILUC	Indirect Land Use Change
ITC	International Trade Centre
ISCC	International Sustainability & Carbon Certification
LAC	Latin American Countries
MERCOSUR	Mercado Común del Sur (Southern Common Market)
NAFTA	North American Free Trade Agreement
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PDO	Protected Designation of Origin
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
PPML	Pseudo Poisson Maximum Likelihood
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEE	South East Europe
SFA	Stochastic Frontier Analysis
VSS	Voluntary Sustainability Standards

Executive Summary

This deliverable has been produced in the context of *Task 2.3. Analysing effects of certification on trade of bio-based value chains*. In particular, this task aims at investigating whether there is a relation between certification and (changes in) traded volumes of bio-based products along the relevant value chains. Important challenges when thinking of empirically investigating this relation are the limited (or lack) of evidence in the existing body of literature, as well as the lack of statistical data, e.g. international oriented databases do not distinguish imports and exports of biological resources and bio-based products towards their (un-)certified origin.

Based on the findings of this literature review, this report sets the basis for future econometric analysis of trade flows of bio-based products and their raw feedstocks when the relevant statistical data becomes available. An initial step in this direction has been taken in the context of *Task 2.2. Data collection and filling gaps on global trade flows for (un)certified biobased value chains*, being the outcome of this task a database of trade volumes for biological resources and bio-based products for those value chains identified in *Task 2.1: Identifying most representative biobased value chains*. Deliverable 2.2 concluded that the production and trade of most biobased final/intermediate products are not explicitly reported in statistics, but in their hybrid forms. Neither of the deliverables provided evidence about the relationship between certified rate of production and trade of EU biobased final/intermediate products.

In *Task 2.3*, the limited amount of specialized literature available on the topic was reviewed. The insights generated from this review include:

- Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) has certainly had an impact on the evolution of trade flows across the globe.
 - The number of certified agricultural commodities has been increasing in the last decade, reflecting the growth of sustainability standards.
 - There has been an important increase in voluntary certification initiatives applicable to agro-food commodities at different stages of the production processes.
 - Imported deforestation is a key concern which should be addressed by policy-makers. To curb this phenomenon, policy-makers in destination countries could rely on: informational instruments, import tariffs, carbon pricing, regulation, capacity building, monitoring and research.
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1. Introduction

1.1 Research question

Keeping in mind the fact that 'bio-based does not necessarily mean sustainable', the present literature review aims at bringing light into the following research question: *Has certification for sustainable standards altered or changed trade flows of bio-based products at international level?*

1.2 Preliminary considerations

When searching for answers to this question, one could think of two initial 'actions':

- Consulting specialised literature on the implementation (and impact) of certification/sustainable standards on bio-based products and related commodities such as food and bio-energy products.
- Reviewing the existing literature on trade (regardless the traded commodity) to identify the standard approach(es) to model trade flows and understanding their determinants.

Although the main focus of this study is on how certification has affected/could affect the trade flows of bio-based commodities it is important to study the potential effects of certification along all the stages of the supply chain. Therefore, there is also a need to examine the impacts of certification on the production/trade of feedstocks (e.g., sugar crops (sugarcane, sugarbeet), oil crops (soy, palm, oilseed rape, sunflower) and starch crops (wheat, potato, etc.)) since they can be used for bio-based applications, as well as for other uses such as food or energy production. From a practical side, another reason for extending the literature review to documents focusing on biomass feedstocks is that the literature on (un)certified trade of intermediate/final biobased products is limited.

Drawing attention to the trade literature, an initial scoping exercise directed us to the study of gravity models. As stated by Wheeler (2005), gravity models are the most common example of spatial interaction modelling. In general terms, gravity models use two variables (population totals and distance) to estimate the volume of spatial interaction between or among places (countries, regions, cities, etc.). Gravity models have been extensively employed for assessing exchanges of resources between locations, being these resources labour (in the case of analyses focusing on migration and commuting), or goods and services (in the case of studies looking at international trade). In the particular case of trade, gravity models 'predicts that the flow of goods between two locations is positively related to their size (or income levels) and negatively related to the distance between them, after controlling for factors that may affect trade (e.g., price differences and differences in the salient features of regulatory frameworks)' (Kanavos and Wouters, 2014).

1.3 Aim

The purpose of this deliverable is twofold. Firstly, the document elaborates on the methodology employed and the criteria used for selecting the relevant contributions. Secondly, it reports on the main findings of the literature review which has been conducted in the context of Task 2.3. Ultimately, the report aims at suggesting the formal specification that could be followed for conducting the relevant econometric analysis when the required statistical data becomes available.

1.4 Structure of the document

After this brief introduction as section 1, the layout of this report is as follows:

- Section 2 describes the methodology employed for the purpose of Task 2.3.
 - Section 3 elaborates on the main findings of the literature review and presents a general conceptual framework that could be used for econometrically analyse the impacts of certification on trade of bio-based products.
 - Section 4 summarises the report and provides some recommendations for future work.
 - The Annex lists of all the materials (scientific articles, reports, websites, etc.) that have been included in this literature review. Key characteristics of each contribution are also reported in this section.
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2. Approach

2.1 Methodology

For the purpose of Task 2.3, an integrative literature review has been conducted using the search terms in Table 1. Synder (2019) suggests carrying out an integrative literature review in those cases in which researchers are dealing with research questions that have a broad scope, being the ultimate objective to design a conceptual framework to understand the question at hand. In the context of an integrative literature review, the relevant search terms are not used in a systematic manner. Research papers, book chapters, grey literature and any other written material are considered.

Table 1: Relevant search terms. Source: Authors.

Broad theme/concept	Key search terms
Bio-based products	Bio-based products, bio-based value chains, biomass feedstock, sustainable biomass, biofuels
Gravity models	Gravity models, gravity equations, gravity analysis, gravity analysis biofuels
Modelling international trade	Econometric modelling trade effects, econometric modelling trade impacts
Trade flows of bio-based products	International trade bio-plastics, international trade biomass, international trade bio-based products, international trade biofuels
Others	Certification, certified products, sustainability, sustainable trade, imported deforestation

The outcome of this exercise was a selection of 38 relevant items. The majority of them are scientific papers (23 out of 38). The lack of specific papers/reports on quantitative analysis of trade flows of bio-based commodities can be explained by the novelty of the topic, as well as for the lack of long and robust time series that allow for such a statistical/econometric analysis.

2.2 Additional considerations

In order to classify the selected contributions, various typologies have been defined. To begin with, Table 2 (next page) provides an overview of several criteria that focus on the type of source (I), the relevance of the topic (II), and the methodology (III). An additional criterion to indicate the contribution of the publication/material to the specialised literature is also included (IV).

Table 2: Key characteristics of selected contributions. Source: Authors.

Type of source (I)	To which extent is the key research question addressed? (II)	Methodology (III)	What is the value added of this contribution? It includes a... (IV)
Journal	Yes (directly)	Qualitative	Data source
Journal (Food Policy)	Yes (indirectly, useful)	Gravity analysis	Monitoring framework
Report	Yes (on certificates)	Econometrics	Method
Handbook	No	Panel data analysis	Model assessment
Dashboard	Yes (interesting but trade is not directly addressed)	Meta analyse	
Database	Yes (background information)	Meta analyse/econometrics	
Website		Multiple meta-regression analysis	
Model		Time series econometrics	
Preprints (website)		Market analysis	
Policy briefs, briefing notes, etc.		Stakeholder database	
Working paper		Blockchain model	
Conference paper		Other	

Table 3 (next page) presents additional typologies that have been used to categorise all the materials under consideration. In particular, other important dimensions that have been considered when searching/reviewing the various sources are the geographical coverage (I and II), the type of commodity under consideration (III), as well as the data source from which the statistical data was obtained (IV).

As already explained, food and energy products have been covered in the literature review although they are outside of the scope of this project (see, column (III)). The reason behind is that there is more literature on these 'traditional' products and some lessons learnt from these commodities can be extrapolated to novel bio-based products.

Table 3: Coverage and data sources. Source: Authors.

Region of origin (I)	Trading partner (II)	Product (III)	Data source (IV)
EU	Global	Biomass	Comext
RoW	EU	Bio-based value chain	ProdCom
Non-EU	Intra-EU	Bio-based sector	FAO
EU/RoW	Intra-EU & Extra-EU	Bio-based energy products	Survey
Intra-EU & Extra-EU	African, Caribbean and Pacific countries	Agri-food products	Interviews
Italy	OECD	Multiple bio-based products	Multiple sources
France	Non-OECD	Others	Others
Sweden			
Germany			
OECD			
CARICOM			
Latin America			
Latin America and the Caribbean			
Colombia			
Asia			
South Korea			
Nigeria			
Global			

NB. 'Not applicable' and 'Not available' are additional options included in each classification.

All these typologies have been used to compile a database in which additional information on the type of indicators/key variables used, together with a short abstract were recorded. A complete list of publications (including its type and key characteristics) is included in the Annex.

3. Literature review

3.1 Sustainability and the role of certification

The introduction of Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) has certainly had an impact on the evolution of trade flows across the globe. More specifically, United Nations (2023) identifies the potential channels through which VSS can affect the volume and the value of traded commodities (Figure 1). From a broader perspective, the implementation of Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) also has important implications for the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SGD) (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Channels of potential VSS impact on trade. Source: Reproduced from United Nations (2023).

As noted by International Trade Centre (2021), the number of certified agricultural commodities has been increasing in the last decade, reflecting the growth of sustainability standards.^{1, 2} These changes are driven by the increasing interest of all market participants, consumers, traders and producers. International Trade Centre (op. cit.) based on the State of Sustainable Markets Report indicates a steady increase in certified acreage in terms of sustainability standards. For a selection of crops, this report concludes that the minimum

¹ See, also, International Trade Centre (2012) for the outcomes of a systematic review on the impacts of private standards regarding several aspects of the supply chain.

² See, also, Ehart (2021) for further details on the implementation of sustainability certifications for wood and forestry products in order to mitigate deforestation. Examples of this type of certifications are Forest Stewardship Council (FSC), the Sustainable Forestry Initiative (SFI), the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) or Responsible Wood (which is the national translation of PEFC in Australia and New Zealand).

certified increased by 52% over the period 2014-2018. Nevertheless, in some sectors it seems that the shares of certified land have stabilized around 20%. The report also points to sectors such as mining, fossil fuels and plastics which seem to be lagging behind in terms of the implementation of sustainability standards. On a positive note, a consultation carried out by International Trade Centre also indicates that 85% of the EU retailers consulted have experienced increased sales of sustainable products over the period 2015-2019, while 92% have positive expectations regarding the sales of sustainable products in the near future.^{3, 4}

Figure 2: VSS and SDG targets. Source: Reproduced from United Nations (2023). Based on Bissinger et al. (2020).

Mol and Oosterveer (2015) concentrate on agro-food commodities and indicate that there has been an important increase in voluntary certification initiatives applicable to products and different stages of the production processes. Certification initiatives support traceability along the supply chain, guaranteeing the sustainability of the relevant products. After highlighting the lack of systematic analysis of traceability systems for sustainability in agro-food supply chains, Mol and Oosterveer (2015) carry out an analysis of four different traceability systems to guarantee sustainability, i.e. mass balance, segregation, identity preserved (or tracking and tracing). The authors conclude that the increasing globalization of markets for sustainable agro-food commodities led to the emergence of book-and-claim traceability systems. Other systems such as identity preservation, segregation and mass balance will also remain important in view of the different drivers of traceability requirements along the various supply chains. Another important conclusion of this study is that traceability is becoming a market on its own, explained by the usual economic and market dynamics. Among the determinants of traceability systems these authors consider consumer identity, extended supply chains, the dominance of institutional actors, low public debate and no inherent quality

³ See, also, International Trade Centre (2018) for further statistical information on production and certified area.

⁴ Other relevant contributions on the topic of sustainability and certification are International Trade Centre, FiBL and IISD (2019a, 2019b) and ISCC (2023).

differences⁵. More recently, Bager et al. (2022) have also investigated the potential role of new technologies such as blockchain to improve sustainability and traceability of agro-food products, more specifically, in the case of coffee. Another agri-food product in which some efforts to improve sustainability in its production are currently occurring is sugarcane (Ferreira et al., 2022).

An important contribution by Sam and Song (2022) analyses the impact of the ISO 14001 certification in increasing exports for those firms that have obtained the mentioned certification. More specifically, the authors econometrically estimate a gravity trade model by means of a panel of South Korean manufacturing industries exporting to 176 countries over the period 1988-2015. They find evidence supporting the fact that the ISO 14001 certification has positively impacted on the exports of the South Korean manufacturing sectors. This impact is not homogeneous across the sample under consideration and depends on factors such as the level of economic development of the destination market. The stronger effects of certification are identified in the case of exports to high-income countries.

Focusing on certified food, Bellassen et al. (2022) estimate 25 indicators for 52 food value chains in order to assess their economic, environmental and social performance. Specifically, this paper investigates whether EU certified food (including organic and geographical indications) is more sustainable than its conventional counterpart, by relying on a sample of twenty-six certified products in thirteen countries.^{6, 7} Overall, this assessment concludes that the average performance of certified food is higher than its conventional reference on most economic and social indicators. In particular, the authors report that certified food is 61% more expensive, while extra-performance per euro is similar to other policy interventions. More specifically, in economic terms, certified products seem to include a price premium (+61%) and manage to translate it into a higher value added (+14%) and operating margin (+31%). Certified food also seems to have positive impacts on the labour market, creating more employment (+14%) with higher productivity (+32%). Nevertheless, the environmental performance of certified food is similar to its conventional counterpart on the most common indicators. In particular, certified products report lower pollutant emissions per hectare basis (– 27% GHG emissions and – 23% water pollution). When emissions are calculated per ton, the mentioned higher performance seems to be overrun by the lower yield of certified farms.

In the context of EU certification, Morone et al. (2021) focus on Italy and explore the potential existence of a ‘green premium’ for bio-based over conventional products, and a ‘certified green premium’ which reveals the willingness to pay of consumers for certified bio-based products over ‘regular’ bio-based products. The authors conclude that social involvement is crucial in order to make certification a useful tool that encourages consumers to make green purchases.

On the methodological side, Hellenic Competition Commission and Netherlands Authority for Consumers and Markets (2021) present an overview of different methodologies that can be applied for a quantitative assessment of the impacts of sustainability under competition law. The selected methodologies could be also applicable to the analysis of the potential impacts of the implementation of sustainable certifications related

⁵ Previously, Oosterveer and Mol (2010) provide an analysis of biofuels trade, paying special attention to issues such as access, trade barriers and sustainability in the case of developing countries.

⁶ The sample includes 9 animal products, 14 vegetal products and 3 unfed seafood/fish products, as well as the following certified products: 7 organic products, 8 PDO products and 11 PGI products.

⁷ Further evidence and discussion on the impacts of geographical indicators on trade flows is provided by De Filippis et al. (2022).

to agri-food, wood, forestry and bio-based commodities, when thinking of analysing specific aspects of trade and beyond such as for example the welfare implications introducing certifications.

3.2 Specialised literature on biofuels and other bio-based commodities

Since commodities such as bio-plastics, bio-paints, bio-cosmetics, etc. are recent developments in the economy, one could wonder whether the literature on biofuels is already addressing the potential impact of the implementation of sustainability standards/certification on biofuels trade⁸. Are there any lessons that can be extrapolated to other bio-based products?

This issue of implementing a certification system for bio-energy trade has been explored by Lewandowski and Faaij (2006). The existence of negative impacts of large-scale biomass production and exports such as deforestation or the competition between food and biomass production require the development of sustainability criteria and certification schemes to better regulate biomass trade. Further to the evaluation of selected certification schemes, the need for developing criteria and indicators to ensure sustainable biomass is restated. These schemes should address both producers and consumers of biomass (and bio-based products), while taking into account the local conditions of the areas in which biomass is produced.

Balugani et al. (2022) concentrate on the impacts of the Renewable Energy Directive II which shifts the focus from Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) environmental impacts to ILUC risk. This contribution presents a spreadsheet tool that brings together ILUC modelling and policy. More specifically, the tool estimates the ILUC risk of bio-based material production, providing relevant insights in terms of by how much different additionality practices can reduce the mentioned risk at the different stages of the value chain. As an illustration, the tool is employed for analysis of two specific cases: maize production in Iowa and in Romania. In the first case, maize production is very intensive and additionality practices have a reduced impact on its ILUC risk category (low-ILUC-risk-produced maize would be around 0.03 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). In the Romanian case, there is considerable room for implementation of additionality practices that could contribute to reducing the ILUC risk (low-ILUC-risk-produced maize is around 0.19 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). The model also takes into account trade efficiencies, i.e. the demand for land that be ultimately transferred to another country. Insights regarding the demand for land in third countries are important when thinking of mitigating imported deforestation.

Several concerns such as deforestation and the competition with other uses such as food surround the use of biomass. Against this background, Harder et al. (2022) extensively discuss the issue of imported deforestation and biomass-related trade issues. As indicated by the authors, a large part of tropical deforestation is caused by an increasing demand for agricultural land. This increasing demand is often driven by the demand of third countries in the global market, particularly of commodities such as beef, palm oil, soybeans or wood. To curb this phenomenon, the following instruments could serve policymaking in consumer countries: informational instruments, import tariffs, carbon pricing, regulation, capacity building, monitoring and research.

Going deeper on the topic, Philippidis et al. (2016) rely on the Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool (MAGNET) in order to model competing uses of biomass to quantify its contribution towards a sustainable

⁸ See, also, Bryngemark and Söderholm (2022) for further empirical evidence and additional discussion on the impact of green industrial policies and domestic production of biofuels.

low carbon economic path. This assessment concludes that there is a role for public policy to play when pursuing lower carbon economic growth, environmental preservation and sustainable biomass usage. Nevertheless, if policies are not well-designed other issues such as resource efficiency or conflict between policy instruments could emerge. Also, by means of the MAGNET model, Sturm and Banse (2021) simulate three different transformation paths to 2050 that the German economy could follow when transitioning towards a bio-based economy. Drivers such as GDP, population developments, trade and land use can play a crucial role by significantly favouring the transition or inhibiting it. In terms of the supply of biomass, productivity increases in agriculture and the reduction of post-harvest losses are very important to alleviate potential competition between uses. Regarding market demand, changes in consumer behaviour and preferences for food are key elements to encourage this transition. The analysis does not consider increased demand for biomass for energy and material use as critical elements in the context of the simulated pathways.

Focusing on the potential of bio-based products to reduce detrimental impacts on the environment, Zuiderveen et al. (2022) investigate the environmental trade-offs of 86 emerging bio-based materials compared to their fossil-based alternatives by means of linear mixed-effects models (LMM). Specifically, the authors estimate response ratios of variables such as GHG emissions, acidification, eutrophication, ozone depletion and photochemical ozone formation footprints by product category, feedstock type and technology readiness levels. Although trade is not directly addressed in this paper, one of the findings of this contribution and the implementation of related policies could eventually affect trade flows. In particular, the authors conclude that for bio-based products to be more environmentally sustainable the negative impacts that emanate at the stage of the cultivation of biomass need to be tackled. Following this line of reasoning, the implementation of certain sustainability standards could potentially negatively affect the available biomass that is produced, leading to lower volumes traded at international level.

Another relevant contribution by Martin et al. (2018) examine bio-based value chains in the case of Sweden and further discuss the concerns related to the sustainability of bio-based products (e.g. overexploitation of biomass resources and indirect impacts of land use, etc.). In particular, this paper presents the outcomes of an evaluation of various life cycle studies of bio-based products regarding the extent to which sustainability indicators that were included in each study. The authors conclude that there is a need for the development and dissemination of improved methodologies that permits to capture environmental impacts, e.g. water depletion, indirect land use change, effects on ecosystem quality and biodiversity. Overall, having a better understanding of the environmental impacts of bio-based products on the local economy and beyond is key to develop proper certification systems that ensures biomass sustainability at the production level, which eventually would lead to sustainable trade of both raw biomass feedstocks and bio-based products.

3.3 Gravity models

A seminal contribution by Chaney (2013) states that the use of gravity models for trade analysis is a very solid case of economic theory. In general terms, gravity models reflect the following assumptions: (i) bilateral trade between two countries is proportional to their size, measured in terms of GDP; and (ii) inversely proportional to the geographic distance between them. At firm level, the second assumption also holds since larger firms tend to export over longer distances on average. More specifically, Chaney (2013) elaborates on the underlying theoretical framework and also provides some discussion on the -1 distance elasticity of trade. On the practical side, Chaney (2013) develops a model in which large firms can endogenously export over longer distances. The author concludes that the impact of distance on aggregate trade depends on the shape of the distribution of firm sizes.

Focusing on the Asian region, Dai et al. (2021) analyse the impact of environmental regulations on trade patterns, with a particular focus on those environmental goods listed by the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) and the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).⁹ For a better understanding of the trade-environmental regulation nexus, the authors estimate a gravity model by relying on a panel which covers 112 exporter countries and 53 importer countries over the period of 1989–2013. The authors find that strict environmental policies hinder trade, being this impact stronger in the case of those environmental goods included in APEC compared to the ones considered by OECD. Nevertheless, despite the negative impacts on trade flows, environmental regulation is needed to promote and encourage the consumption of environmentally-friendly goods.

In terms of the literature with a focus on African countries, Abdullahi et al. (2021) provide some empirical evidence in the case of Nigeria by analysing the determinants and potential of agri-food exports to 70 major trading countries between 1995 and 2019. Econometrically, this study relies on a Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) applied on a gravity model. Moreover, several econometric techniques are applied including fixed effects, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Pseudo Poisson Maximum Likelihood (PPML) and Heckman models. The authors conclude that the economic size (gross domestic product (GDP)) of Nigeria and its trading countries, importers' population, EU membership, ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) membership and contiguity favours agri-food export. In contrast, other factors such as bilateral distance, domestic population, exchange rate and language, negatively affect agri-food exports.

Moving onto the literature with a focus on Latin America, Ayuda et al. (2022) rely on gravity models to disentangle the causes of the strong growth in the agri-food exports that was Latin American countries experienced during the period 1994-2019. The models are estimated by means of several techniques including PPML, OLS, as well as the Heckman selection model. The study concludes that the growth in agri-food exports was driven by both supply and demand elements, although the latter effect was dominating. From a policy perspective, the authors suggest that the development of trade agreements (e.g. NAFTA, MERCOSUR, CACM and APEC among others) has contributed significantly to boost agri-food exports in the region. Moreover, Alleyne and Lorde (2014) analyse trade flows in the context of the CARICOM (Caribbean Community) countries.¹⁰ In this case, the relevant gravity model follows a 'classical' specification including variables such per capita GDP differentials, trade to GDP and languages which have a positive impact. The model also includes additional determinants of trade such as geographical distance, exchange rate and an indicator for historical trade relationships have negative impacts on trade, being the impact of the latter counterintuitive. An important conclusion is that a proper management of the exchange rate is critical, at the same time that CARICOM countries are encouraged to establish trading relationships with other regions with higher living standards.

Balogh et al. (2022) also concentrate on the drivers of agricultural bilateral exports for the period 1995-2019 in the case of Latin American Countries (LAC). The authors conclude that importers' GDP of LAC countries has a stronger effect on agricultural trade compared to LAC exporters. Cultural similarities (measured in terms of common language) and countries' participation in MERCOSUR (*Mercado Común del Sur*) stimulated agri-food export. As could be expected from general economic theory, distance, past colonial links, and North American

⁹ Environmental goods are those which enable sustainable growth and reduce pollution from human activity (Dai et al., 2021).

¹⁰ See, also, Jiménez-García and Rodríguez (2022) for an assessment of the impacts of regional trade agreements in the case of 103 bilateral agreements.

Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) increased trade costs, leading to a negative effect on the export of agricultural commodities. No clear evidence of the role of environmental regulation is identified.

Drawing attention on the EU region, Matkovski et al. (2018) explore the impacts of the liberalization process of the agri-food sector in the Southeastern European (SEE) countries. In this case, the gravity model is estimated by means of a panel which covers the period 2005–2015. Liberalization of the market in the SEE countries seems to have had positive impacts on the total foreign trade of agri-food products. However, the study highlights the need to permit the access to the EU market in an organised manner since these countries have a lower level of competitiveness than the EU countries. Röttgers et al. (2010) also estimate a gravity model which includes additional variables to take into account for zero-inflated trade data. More specifically, the model is expanded using the Heckman approach and augmented by spatial weights. Anderson and Van Wincoop's controls for multilateral resistance are also included. The authors conclude that the mandatory biofuel blending quota has a positive impact, while investment subsidies does not seem to play a role. In contrast, trade integration might even have had detrimental impact on intra-EU trade. The latter reflects an exhausted EU internal market for raw and intermediate materials for biodiesel.

Apart from that, Balogh and Leitão (2019) investigate the effects of geographical proximity, cultural similarity, free trade agreements on bilateral agricultural trade as well as intra-industry trade between EU MSs and their trading partners. The period under consideration for econometrically estimating a gravity model is 1996-2017. An important finding of this article is that EU MS seem to export more agricultural products to their common markets. The authors also find evidence indicating that the export costs of agricultural products are lower if the EU and its non-EU trading partners are culturally similar, have the same religion or there is regional trade agreement in place.

Furthermore, Macedo et al. (2019) also provide evidence confirming the usual relations underlying a generic gravity model in the case of the EU wine sector. In other words, this piece of research suggests that imports are positively related to the importing country GDP. Export propensity is positively related to the existence of regional trade agreements, common language, similarity of religious culture, while export intensity is boosted by common language among others. Both imports and exports negatively affected by distance.

Looking at the forestry sector, Olofsson et al. (2017) analyse those potential factors that could be affecting the trade flows of wood chips and particles (HS4401) and industrial roundwood (HS4403) within the EU28 over the period 20005-2014. The estimated parameters indicate that in the case of HS4401 both the GDP of exporting countries (0.64) and the GDP of the importing countries (0.36) have a positive impact on trade. Regarding HS4403, the econometric analysis suggests that exporting countries GDP negatively affects trade flows (-0.69) while importing countries GDP shows a positive effect (0.80).

For a better understanding of the specific determinants that could be included in the formal specification of a gravity model, Table 4 provides some examples.

Table 4: Specifying a gravity model – selected examples. Source: Authors' compilation based on several sources.

References	Endogenous variable	Exogenous determinants
Sam and Song (2022)	Sum of the total exports of industry k from South Korea to country j in year t	Ratio of ISO 14001 adoption, GDP per capita in country j in year t , Distance between South Korea and country j , Weighted average tariff of manufacturing industry in country j and year t (%), dummy

		variable for bilateral trade agreement between countries, ratio of the number of ISO 14001 certificates to total number of firms in the different industries
Dai et al. (2021)	<p>Model I: Exports of similar goods, which are the products that share the same HS4 commodity code with environmental goods</p> <p>Model II: Exports of environmental goods</p>	Variable capturing environmental provisions, proxy for environmental policy, GDP, GDP per capita, dummy variable for regional trade agreements, dummy variable that takes a value of 1 if the origin i and destination j are contiguous, dummy variable for a common currency, dummy variable for same religious background, average tariff, average tariff for environmental goods, number of clauses relating to environmental provisions, indicators used to control for multilateral resistance terms
Ayuda et al. (2022)	<p>Agri-food exports of country i to country j in year t in real terms, in 2019 USD</p> <p>$i = 15$ Latin American countries</p> <p>$j = 185$ countries</p>	Real GDP exporting country and the importing country, measures the size of the market of each country, geodesic distance, volatility of the bilateral nominal exchange rate, political uncertainty in country, dummy variable that takes the value of 1 if the countries share the same official language, measure of the facility to trade, dummy variable for regional agreement, dummy for indicating WTO membership, gross agricultural production included instead of GDP
Matkovski et al. (2018)	Export of agri-food products in the SEE countries to core EU regions	GDP of the importing country, GDP per capita of the importing country, distance between the countries, a dummy variable which examines the effects of the mutual border on the export of agri-food products of Serbia, a dummy variable, which covers the effects of the CEFTA on the export of agri-food products of the SEE countries, a dummy variable which covers the effects of the SAA on the export of agri-food products of the SEE countries

Abdullahi et al. (2021)	Bilateral agri-food export trade flows between Nigeria and importing country for a given commodity	GDP indicators for both countries, GDP per capita indicators, geographical distance between the capital of Nigeria and the capital of the importing country, population of both countries, set of time-invariant explanatory variables vector (distance, landlocked, language, contiguity), and a set of trade stimulating variables (EU, ECOWAS, colony)
Balogh and Borges Aguiar (2022)	Bilateral aggregated agricultural exports of LAC countries to its destinations	Logarithm of LAC countries GDP (current USD), logarithm of agricultural importers' GDP from LAC (current USD), logarithm of geographic distance between country's most populated cities (km); common official primary language in trading countries; common borders of trading countries; past common colonial relationship of trading countries; trading countries are members of the Southern Common Market; trading countries are members of the North American Free Trade Agreement; the Paris Agreement was ratified
Röttgers et al. (2010)	Imports of canola oil for non-food use into the EU	Distance weights, country fixed effects and weighted trade values, GDP in dollars, variables indicating policy interventions (biofuel quota, capital subsidies), cost production ratios, inverse Mill's ratio, biofuel consumption transport
Olofsson et al. (2017)	Trade of Wood chips and particles (HS4401) and Industrial roundwood (HS4403)	Economic size, distance, common border, common currency, forest endowment
Alleyne and Lorde (2014)	Total trade	GDP, GDP per capita, trade to GDP ratio, population, absolute difference of per capita GDP levels, nominal exchange rate, distance between respective countries

In summary, in order to empirically assess the potential impact of certification on trade flows of bio-based commodities, a gravity model including of the following determinants could be estimated: (i) GDP and GDP per capita; (ii) distance between countries (geodesic distance); (iii) nominal exchange rate; (iv) dummy

variables to account for trade agreements (e.g. EU-MERCOSUR, CARIFORUM-EU, EU-Vietnam, etc.); (v) dummy variables to account for cultural and other socioeconomic factors (e.g. common language, common currency, colonial past); (vi) dummy variables to take into account policies to promote the bioeconomy or support the environmental ambitions; and (vii) dummy variables to represent relevant certification schemes. The reader should keep in mind that the list of exogenous variables needs to be 'tailored' based on data availability and the choice of bio-based products whose supply chains are being analysed. The usual caveats regarding correlation and multicollinearity between variables will also apply during the estimation process.

4. Conclusions

4.1 Concluding remarks

The literature review carried out in the context of Task 2.3 aimed at investigating whether certification have altered traded volumes of selected bio-based products. A limited amount of specialized literature on the topic was available due to the novelty of bio-based economy and the limited statistical data available which prevents researchers from carrying out quantitative analysis.

Nevertheless, this exercise has been insightful and permitted us to identify the following key messages:

- Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) has certainly had an impact on the evolution of trade flows across the globe.
- The number of certified agricultural commodities has been increasing in the last decade, reflecting the growth of sustainability standards.
- There has been an important increase in voluntary certification initiatives applicable to agro-food commodities at different stages of the production processes.
- Imported deforestation is a key concern which should be addressed by policy-makers. To curb this phenomenon, policy-makers in destination countries could rely on: informational instruments, import tariffs, carbon pricing, regulation, capacity building, monitoring and research.

Finally, an important lesson learnt that can be drawn based on previous studies on trade of agri-food (Ayuda et al., 2022) and forestry (Olofsson et al., 2017) commodities is that gravity models can provide the relevant framework of analysis when thinking of assessing the potential impacts of certification/sustainability standards on trade flows.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the literature review, we propose to estimate a gravity model which includes the following exogenous variables: (i) GDP and GDP per capita; (ii) distance between countries (geodesic distance); (iii) nominal exchange rate; (iv) dummy variables to account for trade agreements (e.g. EU-MERCOSUR, CARIFORUM-EU, EU-Vietnam, etc.); (v) dummy variables to account for cultural and other socioeconomic factors (e.g. common language, common currency, colonial past); (vi) dummy variables to take into account policies to promote the bioeconomy or support the environmental ambitions; and (vii) dummy variables to represent relevant certification schemes. This broad list of indicators should be considered as preliminary and be adjusted based on the characteristics of the value chain under consideration, data availability reasons, as well as statistical properties of the data.

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Annex

An overview of the selected contributions that have been reviewed for the purpose of the present exercise, together with some of key characteristics of each contribution are provided in Table 5 (next pages).

Table 5: Literature review

Reference	Source	To which extent the topic is addressed?	Methodology	Product	Region of origin	Trading partner	Main indicator	Other indicators
Abdullahi et al. (2021)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Agri-food products	Nigeria	Global	Bilateral agri-food export trade flows between Nigeria and importing country for a given	GDP indicators for both countries, GDP per capita indicators, geographical distance between the capital of Nigeria and the capital of the importing country, population of both countries, set of time-invariant explanatory variables vector (distance, landlocked, language, contiguity), and a set of trade stimulating variables (EU, ECOWAS, colony)
Alleyne and Lorde (2014)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Other	CARICOM	Not available	Total trade between partnering countries	GDP, GDP per capita, Trade to GDP ratio, population, absolute difference of per capita GDP levels, nominal

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

								exchange rate, distance between respective countries
Ayuda et al. (2022)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Agri-food products	Latin America	Global	Dependent variable = Agri-food exports of 15 Latin American countries to their 185 principal trading partners DEFINITION: agri-food exports of country I to country j in year t in real terms, in 2019 USD, taken from UN COMTRADE	Real GDP, in 2019 USD, of the exporting country and the importing country, measures the size of the market of each country, geographical distance in kilometres (geodesic distance), indicator of the volatility of the bilateral nominal exchange rate, political uncertainty in country, dummy variable that takes the value of 1 if the countries share the same official language, measure of the facility to trade, dummy variable for regional agreement, dummy for indicating WTO membership, gross agricultural production included instead of GDP
Bager et al. (2022)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Blockchain model	agri-food products	Colombia	Denmark	Traceability and transparency	Cupping score, defect score, variety, Fairtrade, 4C, Price, environmental sustainability indicators (e.g. water treatment)

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

								system, no deforestation, renewable energy, etc.), economic/social sustainability indicators (payment of premiums to producers, written contracts, minimum wages, etc.)
Balogh and Borges Aguiar (2022)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	agri-food products	Latin America and the Caribbean	Global	Bilateral aggregated agricultural exports of LAC countries to its destinations (in million USD)	Logarithm of LAC countries GDP (current USD), logarithm of agricultural importers' GDP from LAC (current USD), logarithm of geographic distance between country's most populated cities (km); common official primary language in trading countries; common borders of trading countries; past common colonial relationship of trading countries; trading countries are members of the Southern Common Market; trading countries are members of the North American Free Trade Agreement; the Paris Agreement was ratified

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

Balogh and Leitão (2019)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	agri-food products	EU	African, Caribbean and Pacific countries	Agricultural trade (imports and exports), Grubel–Lloyd index	Exporter's GDP, GDP importer country, distances between capitals, common official language, contiguity, common religion, regional trade agreements, set of bilateral dummies from CEPII
Balugani et al. (2022)	Journal	Yes (interesting but trade is not directly addressed)	Others	Multiple bio-based products	Global	Global	Global land demand	Bio-based production policies, use of co-products, use of residues, soil organic carbon changes, use of degraded or abandoned land, market effects, changes in agricultural yields, use of waste as an alternative biomass for bio-based material production
Bryngemar and Söderholm (2022)	Journal	Yes (background information)	Time series econometrics	Bio-based energy products	OECD	Not available	Domestic ethanol production as a share of total fuel use in the transport sector	Demand-pull instruments in the form of blending mandates, technology-push instruments in the form of government R&D support to biofuel development, fixed effects

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

Chaney (2013)	Working paper	Yes (background information)	Gravity analysis	Others	France	Not available	Number of French exporters	GDP, Distance
Dai et al. (2021)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Others	OECD	OECD/Non-OECD	Model I: Exports of similar goods, which are the products that share the same HS4 commodity code with environmental goods. Model II: exports of environmental goods	Variable capturing environmental provisions, proxy for environmental policy, GDP, GDP per capita, dummy variable for regional trade agreements, dummy variable that takes a value of 1 if the origin i and destination j are contiguous, dummy variable for a common currency, dummy variable for same religions background, average tariff, average tariff for environmental goods, number of clauses relating to environmental provisions, indicators used to control for multilateral resistance terms
Da Silva et al. (2013)	Journal	No	Time series econometrics	Bio-based energy products	Not available	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

De Filippis et al. (2022)	Journal (Food Policy)	Yes (indirectly, useful)	Multiple meta-regression analysis	Agri-food products	EU	Intra-EU & Extra-EU	Regulations, Standards	Not available
Ferreira et al. (2022)	Report	Yes (on certificates)	Qualitative	agri-food products	Global	Global	The report does not focus on a specific indicator	Number of certified mills, sugar production, acreage, small- certified farmers, workers, water consumption, GHG emissions, fertiliser application
Harder et al. (2022)	Policy briefs, briefing notes, etc.	Yes (background information)	Qualitative	Not available	Not available	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable
Hellenic Competition Commission and Netherlands Authority for Consumers and Markets (2021)	Report	No	Qualitative	Not available	Not available	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable
International Trade Centre (2012)	Report	No	Qualitative	Not available	Not available	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable
International Trade Centre (2018)	Report	Yes (on certificates)	Market analysis	agri-food products	Global	Not available	Not applicable	Production volumes, areas

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

International Trade Centre (2021)	Report	Yes (background information)	Qualitative	agri-food products	Global	Not available	Not applicable	Development of sustainability standards over time, number of new standards, certified areas, sustainable sales
International Trade Centre, FiBL and IISD (2019a)	Handbook	Yes (directly)	Market analysis	Agri-food products	EU/RoW	Intra-EU & Extra-EU	Regulations, Standards	Certified production, area
International Trade Centre, FiBL and IISD (2019b)	Dashboard	Yes (directly)	Market analysis	Agri-food products	EU/RoW	Intra-EU & Extra-EU	Regulations, Standards	Certified production, area
ISCC (2023)	Website	Yes (on certificates)	Stakeholder database	Not applicable	EU/RoW	Intra-EU & Extra-EU	# ISCC certificates/plant type	Audit/Process info
Jiménez-García and Rodríguez (2022)	Working paper	Yes (background information)	Econometrics	Not available	Global	Global	Stationary bilateral trade flows	Weight matrix, common latent factors
Lewandowski and Faaij (2006)	Journal	Yes (on certificates)	Qualitative	Biomass	Global	Global	Not applicable	Positive conversion, conservation of genetic diversity, conservation of patches with special conservation value, other measures contributing positively to biodiversity, degree of negative conversion, habitat degradation and pollution, erosion and decrease of soil fertility,

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

								change of ground and surface water levels, pollution by chemicals and fertilizers, disturbance, risk of accidents, land use, overharvesting, introduction of invasive species, other types of negative impact on biodiversity
Macedo et al. (2019)	Journal	Yes (indirectly, useful)	Time series econometrics	Agri-food products	Global	Global	Export propensity, export intensity	GDP pc importer (log), EU importer, Production importer (t-1) (log), Production exporter (t-1) (log), Old World exporter, Exch. rate (log), regional trade agreements, Distance (log), Common language, Religious proximity
Martin et al. (2018)	Journal	Yes (interesting but trade is not directly addressed)	Qualitative	Bio-based value chain	Sweden	Intra-EU	Not applicable	Not applicable
Matkovski et al. (2018)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Agri-food products	Non-EU	EU	Export of agri-food products in the SEE countries to core EU regions	GDP of the importing country, GDP per capita of the importing country, distance between the countries, a dummy variable which

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

								examines the effects of the mutual border on the export of agri-food products of Serbia, a dummy variable, which covers the effects of the CEFTA on the export of agri-food products of the SEE countries, a dummy variable which covers the effects of the SAA on the export of agri-food products of the SEE countries
Mol and Oosterveer (2015)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Qualitative	Not available	Not available	Not available	Traceability	Determinants of traceability systems: consumer identity low, extended supply chain, institutional actors dominant, low public debate, no inherent quality differences.
Morici et al. (2022)	Journal	No	Qualitative	Bio-based product	Not available	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable
Morone et al. (2021)	Journal	Yes (on certificates)	Econometrics	Multiple bio-based products	Italy	Not available	WTP	Green premium, certified green premium, socio-demographics characteristics
Olofsson et al. (2017)	Conference paper	Yes (indirectly, useful)	Gravity analysis	Multiple bio-based products	EU	Intra-EU	Trade between countries	Economic size, distance, common border, common

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

								currency, forest endowment
Oosterveer and Mol (2010)	Journal	No	Qualitative	Bio-based energy products	Global	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable
Philippidis et al. (2016)	Journal	Yes (interesting but trade is not directly addressed)	Others	Bio-based energy products	Global	Global	GTAP model indicators	Not applicable
Röttgers et al. (2010)	Conference paper	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Bio-based energy products	EU	Extra-EU	Imports of canola oil for non-food use into the EU	Distance weights, country fixed effects and weighted trade values, GDP in dollars, variables indicating policy interventions (biofuel quota, capital subsidies), cost production ratios, inverse Mill's ratio, biofuel consumption transport
Sturm and Banse (2021)	Journal	Yes (background information)	Others	Agri-food products	Germany	Global	Allocation of the expenditure on food in Germany in 2015, %-Changes in per capita expenditure of private households on food (2015–2050), Projected allocation of expenditure on food in Germany in 2050, Supply of biofuels	Other MAGNET indicators were calculated (although not reported in the paper)

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

							in Germany (in 1000 tons), Use of fossil fuels and biomass as sources of carbon in chemical industry in Germany, Production quantities of main crops in Germany and worldwide, German trade with selected agricultural products	
Sam and Song (2022)	Journal	Yes (directly)	Gravity analysis	Others	South Korea	OECD/Non-OECD	Sum of the total exports of industry k from South Korea to country j in year t	Ratio of ISO 14001 adoption, GDP per capita in country j in year t, Distance between South Korea and country j, Weighted average tariff of manufacturing industry in country j and year t (%), dummy variable for bilateral trade agreement between countries, ratio of the number of ISO 14001 certificates to total number of firms in the different industries
United Nations (2023)	Report	Yes (on certificates)	Qualitative	Agri-food products	Not available	Not available	Not applicable	Evolution in the number of VSS, Share of certified commodity production in total commodity production

D2.3: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of bio-based value changes, 30/11/2023

Valentin et al. (2022)	Journal	Yes (on certificates)	Econometrics	Agri-food products	EU	Intra-EU & Extra-EU	Economic sustainability indicator, environmental sustainability indicator, social sustainability indicator	Price premium, Gross Operating Margin, Share of value exported within Europe, Local multiplier, Carbon footprint per unit of product, Distance travelled per unit of product, Blue water footprint, Labour to production ratio, Bargaining power distribution, Educational attainment, Gross Value Added, Net result, Share of value exported outside Europe, Share of volume exported within Europe, Share of volume exported outside Europe, Carbon footprint per hectare, Emissions from transportation per unit of product, Green water footprint, Turnover to labour ratio, Stability of the value chain level, Wage level, Gender Equality Index
Zuiderveen et al. (2022)	Preprints (website)	No (trade is not directly addressed)	Econometrics	Multiple bio-based products	Global	Not applicable	Average response ratios	GHG footprints, land use change impacts, TRL (see excel file)

Source: Authors

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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